

Engineering Carbon Emission-aware Machine Learning Pipelines

Erik Johannes Husom
SINTEF
Oslo, Norway
erik.johannes.husom@sintef.no

Sagar Sen
SINTEF
Oslo, Norway
sagar.sen@sintef.no

Arda Goknil
SINTEF
Oslo, Norway
arda.goknil@sintef.no

ABSTRACT

The proliferation of machine learning (ML) has brought unprecedented advancements in technology, but it has also raised concerns about its environmental impact, particularly concerning carbon emissions. To address the imperative of environmentally responsible ML, we present in this paper a novel ML pipeline, named CEMAI, designed to monitor and analyze carbon emissions across the entire lifecycle of ML model development, from data preparation to training and deployment. Our endeavor involves an exhaustive evaluation process underpinned by three industrial case studies. These case studies are structured around the application of ML models to predict tool wear, estimate remaining useful lifetimes, and detect anomalies in the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). Leveraging sensor data originating from CNC machining and broaching operations, our research shows empirically the efficacy of carbon emissions as a dependable metric guiding the configuration of an ML development process. The essence of our approach lies in striking a balance between superior performance and minimal carbon emissions. Our findings reveal the potential to optimize pipeline configurations for ML models in a manner that not only enhances performance but also drastically reduces carbon emissions, thereby underlining the significance of adopting ecologically responsible engineering practices.

ACM Reference Format:

Erik Johannes Husom, Sagar Sen, and Arda Goknil. 2024. Engineering Carbon Emission-aware Machine Learning Pipelines. In *Conference on AI Engineering Software Engineering for AI (CAIN 2024)*, April 14–15, 2024, Lisbon, Portugal. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 11 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3644815.3644943>

1 INTRODUCTION

The carbon footprint of AI, largely associated with the training and operation of machine learning (ML) models, has been a contentious issue. Deep learning, a prominent subfield of AI, often relies on vast computational resources, with energy-hungry data centers powering the training of massive neural networks. The consequence of this computational might is substantial carbon emissions, contributing to the ever-increasing challenges posed by climate change and environmental sustainability. Amid this backdrop, it has become imperative for AI researchers and engineers to find ways to reconcile the remarkable advances in AI with a responsibility to

mitigate its environmental impact [32]. The pursuit of environmentally responsible AI engineering necessitates a fundamental shift in perspective that transcends the singular pursuit of ML model performance to embrace the intertwined objective of sustainability. Our goal in this paper is to address this shift by reimagining how we engineer ML pipelines and models.

We stress the importance of a lifecycle analysis for ML pipelines, with a focus on carbon emissions. This approach heightens our environmental consciousness while exploring avenues to attain optimal predictive accuracy with minimal emissions. Considerable research has been devoted to developing tools for quantifying carbon emissions in ML pipelines. CodeCarbon [5], for instance, is an open-source tool that provides estimates of carbon emissions based on cloud or data center energy consumption and its associated carbon intensity. CarbonTracker [2] is another tool enabling researchers and developers to track and predict the energy consumption and carbon emissions of training deep learning models, offering insights into potential future costs.

Applying such tools to ML pipelines still leaves a number of challenges and unresolved issues. While most existing tools primarily concentrate on quantifying emissions during the training phase, it is essential to acknowledge that the broader ML pipeline involves additional critical phases. For instance, end-to-end latency, real-time decision-making, and continuous data streaming can exert significant carbon impacts. The inference phase, data preprocessing, post-processing, and other non-training components are not to be overlooked, as they can make substantial contributions to carbon emissions. Furthermore, it is crucial to recognize that energy consumption and emissions are subject to notable variations contingent upon the specific hardware components employed. Factors such as interconnected networks, central processing units (CPUs), graphics processing units (GPUs), and tensor processing units (TPUs) play a substantial role, but they are frequently inadequately represented in current metrics and measurement tools. Many of these tools often rely on estimates founded on average power usage and generalized emission factors, which may not sufficiently capture the nuances of real-world conditions. In addition, the actual carbon emissions in practice may deviate considerably from theoretical values, especially when ML model deployment occurs in diverse environmental settings, such as remote sensors compared to urban Internet of Things (IoT) devices. Therefore, recognizing the practicality of emissions in real-world scenarios is of utmost importance.

In this paper, we present and assess CEMAI, a novel ML pipeline designed to monitor and analyze carbon emissions across the entire lifecycle of ML model development (from data preparation to training and deployment). CEMAI has been built on top of an ML pipeline for sensor data repair and predictive maintenance tasks for the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). A distinguishing

This work licensed under Creative Commons Attribution International 4.0 License.

CAIN 2024, April 14–15, 2024, Lisbon, Portugal
© 2024 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).
ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-0591-5/24/04.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3644815.3644943>

feature of CEMAI is its instrumentation of CodeCarbon [5], enabling continuous monitoring of carbon emissions throughout the pipeline’s lifecycle. CEMAI encompasses distinct stages, namely data pre-processing, training, evaluation, and deployment. Within these stages, specific sub-tasks are defined. As a case in point, the model training stage comprises data loading, model training, and evaluation sub-tasks. To ensure a comprehensive account of carbon emissions, we employ CodeCarbon at the sub-task level, thereby aggregating emissions to derive a total for each stage. Notably, in scenarios with concurrent task execution, CEMAI determines individual carbon footprints, amalgamating them to derive a stage’s collective footprint, all the while ensuring no emission metrics overlap or are doubly accounted for. It adopts CodeCarbon further to initiate, suspend, and recommence emission monitoring across sub-tasks, incorporating robust exception-handling mechanisms. Special attention is accorded to instances where tasks might be interrupted prematurely, safeguarding the consistent and precise logging of carbon footprints. In the context of ensemble techniques, CEMAI ensures each model within the ensemble is measured separately, enabling a granular breakdown of carbon emissions.

The pipeline employs Data Version Control (DVC) [14], a tool facilitating the creation and versioning of ML workflows. This inclusion of DVC enables the bypassing of certain pipeline phases, either due to inherent caching or static parameters. For such omissions, CEMAI calculates a representative carbon footprint using historical or mean data and labels it as *emission savings*, emphasizing the inherent benefits of version control in the pipeline.

We conduct experiments with CEMAI across three industrial scenarios rooted in IIoT. These include anomaly detection within CNC milling processes, tool wear prediction during the broaching of airplane turbine discs, and forecasting the residual tool life in piston rod fabrication. Our investigation is structured around two research questions: (i) the identification of the most carbon-intensive stages within the pipeline and their potential optimization avenues and (ii) the impact of hardware selection, encompassing desktop GPUs, high-performance GPU, and CPUs, on the overall carbon footprint of the system. Our findings underscore the value of carbon emission monitoring in strategically configuring pipelines, thereby facilitating the generation of models that harmonize reduced emissions with robust performance. Our main contributions are as follows.

- **Novel Sustainable ML Pipeline.** Our primary contribution is the development of CEMAI, an ML pipeline enabling carbon emission-driven lifecycle analysis. Unique in its integration with CodeCarbon, CEMAI continuously monitors and aggregates carbon emissions throughout its lifecycle, fostering environmentally-conscious ML workflows. This approach underscores the balance between computational efficiency and ecological responsibility.
- **Empirical Evidence.** Through industrial case studies for tool wear prediction, remaining useful lifetime estimation, and anomaly detection in IIoT, we offer empirical evidence of the effectiveness of carbon emissions as a reliable metric for the configuration and operation of ML pipelines.
- **AI engineering dimensions for sustainability.** In the context of sustainability, we need to emphasize designing ML pipelines that balance minimized carbon footprints with

model performance. We propose new AI engineering dimensions (e.g., energy measurement, carbon emission measurement) augmenting dimensions presented by Bosch et al. [3].

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the foundations on quantifying carbon emissions with CodeCarbon and AI engineering dimensions for sustainable ML pipelines. In Section 3, we present the core technical details of CEMAI. Section 4 reports on the evaluation results. Section 5 discusses how CEMAI addresses the new AI engineering dimensions. Section 6 discusses the related work. In Section 7, we present the implications and future work. We conclude the paper in Section 8.

2 FOUNDATIONS

2.1 Green AI Metrics and CodeCarbon

In the pursuit of greener and more sustainable AI engineering, a critical aspect lies in quantifying the environmental footprint of AI models (e.g., ML models) during development and deployment. *Green AI metrics* refer to a set of performance indicators used to assess the environmental impact and energy efficiency of AI models and their development processes. These metrics encompass measurements and assessments related to energy consumption, carbon emissions, and the overall ecological footprint generated throughout the lifecycle of AI models [44]. CodeCarbon [5] is a Python framework that measures and monitors the carbon emissions associated with computational processes (in particular with ML model development). It offers the following features:

- **Carbon Emission Monitoring:** It measures the carbon emissions produced during the execution of a computer program. This includes an in-depth analysis of the energy consumption of the underlying hardware infrastructure.
- **Real-time Tracking:** One of its distinguishing attributes is its ability to provide real-time tracking of carbon emissions, enabling developers to make informed decisions regarding the environmental impact of their ML projects.
- **Customizable Reporting:** CodeCarbon generates detailed reports, which can be customized to fit specific requirements. These reports offer insights into the energy usage and carbon emissions, aiding in the selection of the most eco-friendly configurations and practices.
- **Integration with Source Code:** It can be seamlessly integrated into the source code, for example ML pipelines and continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD) processes, allowing for automated environmental impact assessments as a part of ML model development.

CodeCarbon is designed to be unobtrusive, introducing minimal computational overhead while delivering precise energy consumption measurements. It employs a scheduler that periodically records energy metrics, typically every 15 seconds, ensuring continuous and detailed tracking. It records not only the energy consumption but also metadata, such as the number of GPUs employed, hardware specifications, operating system details, and geographical location. The location data can be used to determine the carbon intensity of the local power grid, which subsequently informs the calculation of carbon emissions based on energy consumption.

CodeCarbon uses knowledge about the carbon intensity for various regions and countries [30] to find the amount of emissions produced during computation. The emissions are measured in kilograms of CO₂-equivalents (CO₂eq), a standardized metric used to express the global warming potential of various greenhouse gases, equating their impact to that of CO₂. Additionally, it comprehensively assesses the energy distribution between CPU, RAM, and GPU, ensuring a granular understanding of the resource utilization.

2.2 AI Engineering for Sustainable ML Pipelines

AI engineering is a new discipline focused on developing tools, systems, and processes to enable the application of AI in real-world settings [3, 4, 10]. The goal of AI engineering is to address the engineering challenges of AI systems from the software engineering point of view. One engineering challenge is to design ML pipelines that minimize the carbon footprint while maintaining the performance of the output ML models. Below, we propose and briefly describe some new AI engineering dimensions concerning carbon emission-guided engineering of ML pipelines.

- **Energy Consumption:** Measure the energy usage of ML training and inference processes. This includes the computational resources, hardware, and infrastructure.
- **Carbon Emission Measurement:** Calculate the carbon emissions associated with the energy consumption. Consider the carbon intensity of the energy sources used (e.g., fossil fuels vs. renewables) when calculating emissions.
- **Hardware Efficiency:** Evaluate the efficiency of the hardware used for ML tasks. This can involve assessing the power consumption and energy efficiency of GPUs, TPUs, or other hardware accelerators.
- **Algorithm Efficiency:** Analyze the energy efficiency of ML algorithms and models. Some algorithms may be more computationally intensive and require more energy for training and inference.
- **Data Impact:** Consider the energy and emissions associated with data collection, storage, and preprocessing. Large datasets and complex data processing pipelines can have a significant impact.
- **Infrastructure Location:** Consider the location of data centers or cloud providers. Different regions may use different energy sources, which can affect the carbon footprint.
- **Scalability:** Assess how the energy consumption scales with the size and complexity of ML models and tasks. This dimension is important when considering the environmental impact of large-scale ML model deployments.
- **Model Deployment:** Examine the energy consumption of deploying and running ML models in various scenarios.
- **Optimization Strategies:** Explore strategies for optimizing ML pipelines to reduce energy consumption and emissions without compromising performance.

2.3 ML Pipeline for IIoT

ML offers a promising solution for prediction and data repair tasks in IIoT where ML models can learn correlations among data sources (sensors), enabling the predictive maintenance (e.g., predicting tool wear and useful remaining lifetime), the substitution of sensors,

Figure 1: ML Pipeline for IIoT.

prediction of missing values, and generation of new data to replace corrupt data [12, 35–37, 42]. ML-based data repair techniques can be deployed at the edge [42] or in the cloud [35], leveraging available training data to create containerized repair services for real-time data repair. Figure 1 presents an ML pipeline for IIoT data.

The *input* is multi-variate time series data X from input sensors and univariate time series data y from a target sensor. The *output* is an ML model predicting time-varying measurements of the target sensor (e.g., measurements of tool wear, erroneous data). The input (X, y) goes through three stages:

Stage 1: Data preprocessing. This stage prepares input data for the following stages in several sub-stages: *data profiling*, *data cleaning*, *feature engineering*, *splitting test/training data*, *data scaling*, and *splitting data into sub-sequences*. Data profiling computes the non-linear *maximum information coefficient* [27] and linear *Pearson's correlation coefficient* [33] to find correlations between data columns of different sensors. It generates statistical quantities for each column and alerts if any column has several zeros or missing values. Data cleaning uses this output to automatically remove unwanted data (e.g., columns with several constant or null values).

Feature engineering extracts statistical properties (*features*) from raw input data that exhibit invariance to noise. Furthermore, the feature-based representations of time-series data [18] perform well in classifying tasks at a fraction of the computational cost of processing raw time-series. The input and output data are split into *training* and *test* datasets. The training set is used to train the ML model and tune hyper-parameters in Stage 2. The test dataset is locked away during training and used as an unbiased dataset to evaluate virtual sensor performance in Stage 3.

The datasets contain measurements from different sensors with varying value ranges and are, thus, scaled [17] for a comparable influence during training. The training (including validation

dataset) and test datasets are *restructured* into input and output sub-sequences of the specified *window size* since predictions rely on a window of time-varying observations from input sensors and the desired window of output values.

Stage 2: Training ML model. Our pipeline uses the input and output sub-sequences (of chosen input and output *window sizes*) from Stage 1 to train the ML model. It enables the specification of learning parameters and the selection of ML model types (architectures). The pipeline can support several models, e.g., Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), XGBoost (XGB), DNNs/FCNNs, CNNs [16], and LSTMs [9], to predict the time-varying values of a target sensor. Before training, the pipeline sets apart a small portion of the training data (e.g., 20%) to use as a *validation dataset*. It automatically stops training the model if the prediction error of the validation dataset stops improving, preventing the over-fitting of the model to the training data.

Stage 3: Evaluating model performance. The test dataset is an unforeseen dataset used to evaluate the model performance to minimize bias due to hyper-parameter tuning in Stage 2. Model output and ground truth are compared to assess how well the model predicts the target variable. To this end, the pipeline generates the plots of predictions on test data. Mean Squared Error (MSE), coefficient of determination (R^2 score), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) are used to evaluate the model performance.

The trained, validated, and evaluated model is embodied as a service with an API. The API is invoked using subsequences of data (of size $window_i$) from input sensors and returns a set of target sensor values (of size $window_o$) with time stamps. The raw input sequences cannot always be used by the model as they are since the model is trained on input data features extracted from raw data and bounded (e.g., values between 0 and 1) by a scaling operation.

3 CEMAI APPROACH

CEMAI is conceived and executed as an extension of a pre-existing ML pipeline [35–37, 42], detailed in Section 2.3. This pipeline encompasses multiple successive stages, collectively contributing to the augmentation of data quality, the training of ML models, and the seamless facilitation of their ongoing deployment as operational services. Figure 2 provides a high-level overview of CEMAI. While the pipeline detailed in Section 2.3 was originally designed for data repair and virtual sensor deployment, CEMAI expands its functionalities to prioritize the adoption of energy-efficient ML models and decrease the footprint of the development process (i.e., the environmental impact associated with creating and training ML models). It enables engineers to answer some essential questions:

- Which model is the optimal choice when considering both energy efficiency and performance?
- What is the cost of running inference with a given model, possibly including preprocessing raw input data if needed?
- What part of the pipeline is the most computationally expensive, and where is it easiest to save cost?
- What is the cost of providing explanations for the predictions of a model?
- What is the energy consumption of training a model in case it has to be retrained and/or updated at a later point?
- What is the total carbon footprint of model development?

Figure 2: High-level representation of CEMAI focusing on carbon emission-driven lifecycle analysis. Each pipeline stage undergoes energy usage monitoring, while every execution is meticulously tracked in an emissions log. Following each stage, the resulting output is stored in the cache, and the control parameters of that stage are associated with a hash of the input data and the source code, enabling the retrieval of prior output data from the cache when these components remain unchanged from a previous iteration. This process, as depicted in the diagram, illustrates a scenario where Stage 3 is bypassed, and the anticipated output is retrieved from the cache, serving as the input for Stage 4.

CEMAI adopts two pivotal concepts aimed at mitigating energy consumption and curtailing carbon emissions in ML applications, elucidated in Figure 2. The first concept, *Green AI metrics*, involves comprehensive measurements of energy consumption across all stages of the ML pipeline. These metrics empower users to make informed decisions when selecting models, ensuring a balanced consideration of performance and environmental impact. Additionally, they aid in identifying pipeline segments that demand the most resources, guiding users toward optimizing energy efficiency during both the development and deployment of ML models. The second concept revolves around *Green Pipeline Orchestration*, targeting the reduction of overall energy consumption throughout the developmental process. It principally achieves this by circumventing unnecessary re-execution of processing stages during ML experiments. Subsequently, we delve into the implementation of these concepts in CEMAI.

CEMAI utilizes CodeCarbon [5] for quantifying actual energy consumption. CodeCarbon offers diverse integration methods into the source code, such as explicit objects, function decorators, and context managers. These mechanisms enable us to comprehensively monitor the entire pipeline while maintaining precise control over its segments and stages. In our specific implementation, we predominantly leverage function decorators to trace energy consumption. Each pipeline stage is associated with its dedicated function, encapsulated by a CodeCarbon decorator. The primary advantage of employing function decorators is their capability to ensure uninterrupted and recorded tracking regardless of potential errors occurring during function execution. Contrastingly, when utilizing an explicit object from CodeCarbon for tracking, two distinct calls—initiating and concluding tracking—are necessary. In scenarios where an error, like improperly formatted input data, interrupts the process between these calls, the tracking data might not be written to disk due to the absence of the concluding call. Recording the footprint of pipeline runs that conclude with errors is crucial, particularly for researchers aiming to report the complete emissions generated by their experiments.

Figure 3: Practical Implementation of CEMAI as an Extension of the IIoT-based ML pipeline in Figure 1. Containerized using Docker for reliable and versatile deployment across systems, CEMAI embodies a comprehensive ML pipeline at its core, consisting of two interrelated but distinct pipelines: "Training pipeline" and "Inference pipeline."

CEMAI employs DVC [13] for *green pipeline orchestration*. While DVC offers various features beneficial for managing pipelines—such as seamless integration with Git for data and model version control and reproducible workflows—the foremost advantage within CEMAI is the caching of intermediate outputs between pipeline stages. In operation, a user provides a dataset and a configuration file detailing control parameters for each pipeline stage. The file also includes specifications for ML algorithms, feature engineering methods, data scaling procedures, specific hyperparameters, and other relevant choices. DVC vigilantly monitors alterations to these control parameters in the configuration file, the actual source code of the pipeline stages, and the generated hashes of input and output data for each stage. Leveraging this output, DVC can be used to efficiently discern if a pipeline stage has been executed with an identical configuration as a prior experiment. In such cases, it skips redundant stages and retrieves the correct output from the cache.

The functionality of skipping redundant stages based on identical configurations, as monitored and managed by DVC, can be referred to as "smart caching" or "configuration-based optimization." This capability allows CEMAI to intelligently recognize and skip the execution of its stages if their configurations match prior executions, efficiently retrieving the accurate output from the cache instead. It motivates us to delineate distinct stages for each sub-process that significantly transforms the data. While this pipeline design may entail additional overhead and increased disk space usage due to storing interim results in the cache, the trade-off is justifiable. The design is valuable since the development of ML

models involves numerous iterations of trial and error with diverse control parameters to yield models of satisfactory performance. To prevent redundant recomputation, specific computationally intensive processes are isolated into separate stages. An example of these intensive processes is the process of generating explanations for model predictions using eXplainable AI (XAI) techniques [7], such as SHAP [19, 20, 31] and LIME [28, 29]. Such processes, vital for understanding model outputs, can be computationally demanding. By segregating them, users can experiment with different XAI methods and control parameters without rerunning the overall evaluation, thus enhancing efficiency and avoiding unnecessary repetition.

Figure 3 showcases the practical implementation of the high-level conceptual depiction of CEMAI (as illustrated in Figure 2) as an extension of the IIoT-based ML pipeline featured in Figure 1. CEMAI is containerized via Docker, ensuring its reliable deployment across diverse systems. At the core of CEMAI lies the ML pipeline, depicted in Figure 3 as comprising two distinct but interconnected pipelines: the "Training pipeline" and the "Inference pipeline." Both pipelines share the same foundational source code. However, the inference pipeline exclusively executes the stages necessary for data preprocessing and inference, while the training pipeline encompasses all stages essential for ML model development. Notably, all stages within these pipelines undergo energy usage tracking utilizing CodeCarbon. The pipeline's output, along with the intermediate cache between stages, is stored in a Docker volume to ensure persistent data storage even upon closure of the Docker container. CEMAI also features a user interface providing

an overview of available models, highlighting metrics related to both performance and carbon footprint. This interface serves for both model creation and model inference purposes. For model creation, the user supplies the training data and pipeline configuration, and the resultant model assets essential for conducting inference are saved in model storage. These assets encompass details on data scaling, feature selection, and the model itself. During inference, the user selects a model and provides input data for predictions, facilitated through the user interface or a built-in API.

4 EXPERIMENTS

We conduct experiments with our approach on three industrial case studies to address two Research Questions (RQs):

- **RQ1.** *What are carbon emissions in different stages of the pipeline and can they be optimized?*
- **RQ2.** *How does the choice of hardware affect the overall carbon emissions of the pipeline?*

4.1 Experiment Design

Datasets. Our evaluation used three IIoT datasets, including actual time-series sensor data from three manufacturing machines: Turning machine manufacturing piston rods, broaching machine broaching airplane turbine discs, and Bosch Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machine processing aluminum workpieces. We applied CEMAI to (i) categorize signals (normal and anomalous) in Bosch CNC dataset, (ii) predict tool wear (the gradual failure of cutting tools due to regular operation) in the Broaching dataset, and (iii) estimate the remaining useful lifetime of a tool in the Piston Rod dataset. Table 1 provides a summary of the datasets.

Bosch CNC dataset contains vibration behavior captured from three different CNC milling machines executing 15 processes [40], including normal and anomalous conditions. Tri-axial accelerometers were mounted in each machine, measuring acceleration in X, Y, and Z-axes at a sampling rate of 2 kHz. For the training set, we selected a sequence with no anomalies, while for the test set, we chose a data sequence containing both normal and anomalous data.

Piston Rod dataset was recorded during the machining process of piston rods (pneumatic cylinder components) at the Center for Industrial Productivity (CiP) learning factory in Darmstadt, Germany. The piston rods made of stainless steel were manufactured in batches of four in a turning machine. The machine was equipped with a Siemens 840d CNC control streaming relevant internal signals to a host PC storing the data. The dataset contains the part IDs, machine control data, and timestamp information on when tools were changed in the lathe. The process data (machine control data) includes torque, current, spindle speed, and feed rate for every record with a sampling rate of 5 Hz.

Broaching dataset was collected from three broaching tools in a broach tool holder broaching fifty slots for around three hours. Broaching is a manufacturing process for forming internal or external round, flat, or contoured surfaces. A broaching machine pushes a multi-toothed cutting tool, a broach, into a workpiece to remove material. Slots of various dimensions are cut at high production rates. We had three data sources: (i) two accelerometers with a sample rate of 12.8 kHz, (ii) a data logger with a rate of 250 Hz, and (iii) tool wear measured in millimeters with an optical microscope.

Table 1: Summary of the datasets.

Dataset	Machine	Task	#Train	#Test
Piston Rod	Turning	Useful Lifetime	332,919	83,229
Broaching	Broaching	Tool wear	3,072,024	2,048,016
Bosch CNC	CNC	Anomaly	1,168,434	1,168,434

Setup. We implemented CEMAI using Python 3, Scikit-Learn libraries [24], DVC [13], TensorFlow [23], LIME [28], and SHAP [21]. All experiments, except those run on the cloud server, were performed on a Linux machine with 32 GB RAM, an Intel Core i7-10850H CPU @ 2.70GHz processor with 12 cores, and an NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000 GPU. The cloud server used for the experiments for RQ2 had an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6126 CPU @ 2.60GHz processor with 8 cores and 32 GB RAM, and two NVIDIA A30 GPUs.

For uniformity across experiments, we applied identical configurations of ML algorithms to all datasets. Traditional ML methods—Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), and XGBoost (XGB)—utilized default parameters from Scikit-Learn. The Deep Neural Network (DNN) employed an eight-layer architecture with 64 nodes, while the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) featured eight layers with 64 kernels (kernel size: 3) and four fully connected layers with 64 neurons. LSTM consisted of one layer with 64 units and four fully connected layers with 64 neurons. ReLU served as the activation function, and we employed a learning rate of 0.001 in all neural networks.

Feature engineering in our experiments involved computing the sum, maximum, minimum, range, gradient, standard deviation, and slope from a window of time series data. The selected features were consistent across use cases, but the window size (w) was tailored for optimal performance in each scenario: $w = 4096$ for Bosch, $w = 10$ for piston rod, and $w = 128000$ for broaching. For CNN and LSTM, designed for multi-dimensional data, input sequences with a length (l) were used. In Bosch, $l = 8$; in piston rod, $l = 5$; and in broaching, $l = 100$. The choice of l was manual, based on achieving the highest performance for each use case.

4.2 Results

This section discusses the results of our case studies, addressing, in turn, each of the RQs.

RQ1: What are carbon emissions in different stages of the pipeline and can they be optimized? To address RQ1, we computed the carbon emissions and performance of different CEMAI configurations in our three datasets. We compared several models, i.e., DT, RF, GB, XGB, DNN, CNN, and LSTM, with and without feature engineering (FE). Each stage of the pipeline—*Profile, Clean, Featurize, Split, Scale, Sequentialize, Combine, Train, Evaluate, and Explain*—contributes to the total carbon emissions measured in grams of CO₂ equivalent (gCO₂eq). We assessed the performance of each model configuration using the F₁ score (for the Bosch CNC dataset) and R² score (for the Piston Rod and Broaching datasets). Tables 2-4 list the carbon emissions at different stages of CEMAI for the Bosch CNC, Piston rod, and broaching datasets, respectively.

Bosch CNC Dataset: The 'Train' and 'Evaluate' stages tend to have higher emissions in Table 2, particularly for complex models like LSTM (0.523 for 'Train'). One way to address these higher emissions is to minimize the computational load. DT and RF models

Table 2: The carbon emissions per stage and the performance (measured using the F_1 score) for the Bosch CNC machining case study. All ML algorithms are tested both with and without feature engineering (FE) on the input data.

Model	Carbon emissions per stage (gCO ₂ eq)											F ₁
	Profile	Clean	Featurize	Split	Scale	Sequentialize	Combine	Train	Evaluate	Explain	Total	
DT	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0009	0.0000	0.0022	0.0026	0.0084	0.0141	0.08
DT w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0012	0.0000	0.0021	0.0026	0.0212	0.0271	1.00
RF	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0137	0.0137	0.03
RF w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0214	0.0004	0.0266	0.0483	1.00
GB	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0009	0.0000	0.0163	0.0004	0.0169	0.0345	0.00
GB w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0012	0.0000	0.0753	0.0029	0.0234	0.1028	1.00
XGB	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0009	0.0000	0.0013	0.0030	0.0128	0.0180	0.02
XGB w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0012	0.0000	0.0007	0.0031	0.0631	0.0681	1.00
DNN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	0.0401	0.0029	0.0312	0.0744	0.81
DNN w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0013	0.0001	0.0004	0.0005	0.0004	0.0297	0.0025	0.0607	0.0958	0.00
CNN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000	0.0880	0.0030	0.0003	0.0916	0.00
CNN w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0005	0.0004	0.0900	0.0030	0.0005	0.0944	0.00
LSTM	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000	0.5231	0.0058	0.0002	0.5292	0.00
LSTM w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0005	0.0000	0.5184	0.0058	0.0003	0.5251	0.00

Table 3: The carbon emissions per stage and the performance (measured using the R^2 score) for the piston rod case study. All ML algorithms are tested both with and without feature engineering (FE) on the input data.

Model	Carbon emissions per stage (gCO ₂ eq)											R ²
	Profile	Clean	Featurize	Split	Scale	Sequentialize	Combine	Train	Evaluate	Explain	Total	
DT	0.0000	0.0000	0.0095	0.0000	0.0003	0.0003	0.0002	0.0042	0.0015	0.0007	0.0168	0.23
DT w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0549	0.0002	0.0012	0.0012	0.0010	0.0297	0.0016	0.0046	0.0944	0.45
RF	0.0000	0.0000	0.0096	0.0000	0.0003	0.0003	0.0002	0.1824	0.0023	0.0027	0.1977	0.50
RF w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0549	0.0002	0.0012	0.0011	0.0010	1.8146	0.0022	0.0069	1.8821	0.06
GB	0.0000	0.0000	0.0093	0.0000	0.0003	0.0003	0.0002	0.0535	0.0016	0.0008	0.0660	0.30
GB w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0553	0.0002	0.0013	0.0011	0.0010	0.5964	0.0016	0.0048	0.6618	0.18
XGB	0.0000	0.0000	0.0093	0.0000	0.0003	0.0003	0.0002	0.0052	0.0016	0.0008	0.0177	0.47
XGB w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0549	0.0002	0.0012	0.0011	0.0010	0.0434	0.0016	0.0054	0.1088	0.29
DNN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0095	0.0000	0.0003	0.0002	0.0002	0.0245	0.0016	0.0049	0.0413	0.07
DNN w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0552	0.0002	0.0012	0.0010	0.0010	0.0237	0.0017	0.0286	0.1126	0.12
CNN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0096	0.0000	0.0003	0.0002	0.0002	0.0437	0.0017	0.0054	0.0613	0.02
CNN w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0548	0.0002	0.0012	0.0010	0.0010	0.0607	0.0018	0.0187	0.1395	0.21
LSTM	0.0000	0.0000	0.0094	0.0000	0.0003	0.0002	0.0002	0.2080	0.0023	0.0105	0.2310	0.08
LSTM w/FE	0.0000	0.0000	0.0546	0.0002	0.0012	0.0010	0.0010	0.2482	0.0024	0.0252	0.3339	0.21

Table 4: The carbon emissions per stage and the performance (measured using the R^2 score) for the broaching case study. All ML algorithms are tested both with and without feature engineering (FE) on the input data.

Model	Carbon emissions per stage (gCO ₂ eq)											R ²
	Profile	Clean	Featurize	Split	Scale	Sequentialize	Combine	Train	Evaluate	Explain	Total	
DT	0.1291	0.0197	0.0004	0.0001	0.0002	0.0021	0.0002	0.0113	0.0015	0.0601	0.2247	1.22
DT w/FE	0.1291	0.0197	0.0083	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0014	0.0015	0.0022	0.1625	0.91
RF	0.1291	0.0197	0.0026	0.0000	0.0002	0.0021	0.0002	1.1697	0.0000	0.0000	1.3237	0.76
RF w/FE	0.1291	0.0197	0.0083	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0014	0.0017	0.0622	0.2227	0.83
GB	0.1291	0.0197	0.0034	0.0001	0.0003	0.0025	0.0002	0.1608	0.0059	0.0634	0.3859	0.12
GB w/FE	0.1291	0.0197	0.0083	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0014	0.0018	0.0056	0.1662	0.92
XGB	0.1291	0.0197	0.0004	0.0001	0.0002	0.0021	0.0002	0.0336	0.0043	0.0829	0.1599	0.17
XGB w/FE	0.1291	0.0197	0.0055	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0014	0.0015	0.0026	0.1599	0.70
DNN	0.1291	0.0197	0.0004	0.0001	0.0002	0.0004	0.0002	0.0317	0.0030	0.1631	0.3479	10.80
DNN w/FE	0.1291	0.0197	0.0067	0.0004	0.0036	0.0009	0.0015	0.0430	0.0031	0.1835	0.3915	0.48
CNN	0.1291	0.0197	0.0004	6.1989	0.0002	0.0004	0.0002	0.0016	0.0015	0.0601	0.2134	0.08
CNN w/FE	0.1291	0.0197	0.0067	0.0004	0.0013	0.0022	0.0040	0.2112	0.0044	0.1323	0.5112	0.04
LSTM	0.1291	0.0197	0.0004	0.0001	0.0002	0.0004	0.0002	8.3925	0.0240	0.4471	9.0137	0.01
LSTM w/FE	0.1291	0.0197	0.0083	0.0000	0.0000	0.0034	0.0004	11.0341	0.0240	0.3863	11.6053	0.08

have relatively low emissions compared to more complex models. Feature engineering (FE) increases emissions, as seen in the 'Explain' stage for DT with FE (0.021) compared to DT without FE (0.008). The GB model with FE also sees a significant increase in emissions during the 'Train' stage (0.075). One could focus on simpler models without FE when suitable, as they achieve acceptable F_1 scores (e.g., RF without FE has an F_1 of 0.0261) with lower emissions. However, FE's contribution to achieving perfect F_1 scores (e.g., RF w/FE, GB w/FE, XGB w/FE with F_1 of 1.0) must be weighed against the increased emissions.

Piston Rod Dataset: Training generally incurs the highest carbon emissions (see the *TRAIN* column in Figure 3), notably for RF with FE (RF w/FE) and LSTM with FE (LSTM w/FE) at 1.814 and 0.248, respectively. Feature engineering (*Featurize* in Figure 3) also significantly increases emissions, as seen with DT with FE (DT w/FE) at 0.054 compared to without at 0.009. There is a trade-off between model performance (R^2) and carbon emissions. Higher-performing models like RF and XGB without FE have moderate emissions (0.197 and 0.0176) but good performance (R^2 of 0.499 and 0.470). However, the model performance does not always improve significantly with FE, as seen with RF w/FE where R^2 drops to 0.0612 but emissions increase to 1.882. In contrast, LSTM with FE (LSTM w/FE) has a balance of better performance (R^2 of 0.214) with higher yet reasonable emissions (0.333). We could focus on reducing emissions during the training phase and carefully considering the cost-benefit of FE, aiming for minimal emissions without substantially sacrificing model performance.

Broaching Dataset: Carbon emissions across the CEMAI stages vary with ML models and the inclusion of FE (see Table 4). For instance, the DT model without FE has high emissions at the 'Explain' stage (0.060) relative to other stages, while DT with FE significantly reduces the 'Explain' emissions to 0.00216, optimizing the carbon footprint with a better R^2 score (0.908). RF with FE increases 'Explain' emissions to 0.062 but improves R^2 (0.833), suggesting a trade-off between emissions and performance. GB with FE reduces 'Train' emissions from 0.160752 to 0.001426 while enhancing R^2 to 0.924. LSTM, especially with FE, shows the highest total emissions (11.605) with negative performance ($R^2 = -0.080$), indicating a poor trade-off. In contrast, models like XGB with FE maintain a lower emission profile (0.159 total) while achieving a substantial R^2 score (0.698), suggesting an optimal balance. Optimizing stages like 'Train' and 'Explain' could further reduce emissions while maintaining or enhancing model performance.

RQ1 Conclusion. The 'Train' and 'Evaluate' stages emit the most CO_2 in our datasets, especially with complex models. Feature engineering (FE) increases emissions but can improve performance, as seen in models like GB with FE. There is a performance-emission trade-off, with simpler models without FE offering a balance, while advanced models with FE, like LSTM, may not justify their high emissions despite better performance. Decreasing emissions focuses on reducing the computational load in the 'Train' and 'Explain' stages.

RQ2: How does the choice of hardware affect the overall carbon emissions of the pipeline? To answer RQ2, we evaluated carbon emissions for the top-performing models in each use case

Table 5: Carbon emissions of the best performing models on three hardware configurations.

Case study	Model	Carbon emissions (gCO ₂ eq)		
		Laptop (CPU)	Laptop (GPU)	Cloud
Piston Rod	RF	0.2502	0.1977	1.1420
Broaching	DT w/FE	0.1164	0.1625	0.6431
Bosch CNC	DT w/FE	0.0349	0.0271	0.1608

across three hardware configurations: (i) a CPU-only laptop, (ii) a laptop with both CPU and GPU, and (iii) a cloud server with GPU hardware specialized for AI inference. The dataset sizes vary considerably (from hundreds of thousands to several million data points), limiting direct comparisons across datasets.

Table 5 summarizes our hardware experiments. Comparing GPU and CPU configurations in laptops reveals that, in general, GPU-equipped laptops exhibit better carbon efficiency than their CPU counterparts. For instance, in the Bosch dataset, GPU configurations emitted 0.0271 gCO₂eq compared to 0.0349 gCO₂eq by the CPU setup, demonstrating lower emissions. The heightened computational efficiency of GPUs, leading to shorter processing times, likely contributes to this reduced carbon footprint. This underscores the significance of hardware choice in carbon emissions and suggests that GPU-based configurations may offer a more environmentally friendly option for computationally intensive ML tasks.

In addition to the observed environmental benefits of using a GPU-configured laptop over one without, there is a substantial difference in carbon emissions between laptop and cloud-based configurations. Laptops with GPU consistently exhibited significantly lower carbon emissions across all datasets. For example, using an RF model in the Piston Rod dataset, the GPU-equipped laptop emitted only 0.1977 gCO₂eq, while the cloud setup emitted 1.1420 gCO₂eq. This trend persisted across various models and datasets, emphasizing that local processing can have an environmental advantage over cloud-based solutions for some use cases. The higher carbon emissions in cloud-based computation could be attributed to several factors, e.g., large-scale GPUs prioritizing computational power over energy efficiency and potential inefficiencies in data transfer between CPU and GPU. The results underscore the importance of considering the entire hardware ecosystem, including infrastructure efficiency, rather than focusing solely on computational power. These findings suggest that local processing may offer a more carbon-efficient alternative for some ML tasks running on moderate datasets (in size).

Specialized low-emission hardware for ML tasks holds promise, given the variations in carbon emissions linked to hardware choices. The case for developing and adopting hardware optimized for performance and reduced environmental impact is compelling.

RQ2 Conclusion. Hardware choice significantly influences computational efficiency and carbon footprint in ML pipelines. Our findings show that laptops, with and without GPUs, consistently exhibit lower carbon emissions than the cloud server we utilized, highlighting the potential environmental efficiency of local processing for some use cases. They suggest the potential for developing specialized, low-emission hardware for ML tasks, achieving a balance between performance and ecological impact.

4.3 Threats to Validity

Internal Validity. Internal validity threats stem from fixed configurations in data preprocessing and hyperparameters. The reliance on default parameters for traditional ML and fixed settings for deep learning may not capture optimal dataset configurations. Manual selection of window size and sequence length, tailored for performance in each use case, introduces potential bias in model efficiency and subsequent carbon emission calculations.

External Validity. The study’s focus on three IIoT datasets may limit the generalizability of findings to other domains or dataset types with distinct characteristics or sizes. Additionally, the results on hardware efficiency and carbon emissions are specific to the tested configurations and may not extend to other CPUs or GPUs.

Construct Validity. The carbon emission measurement methodology does not consider all factors, such as indirect emissions from hardware production and maintenance. Relying on a single performance metric for model evaluation may not fully capture model efficacy, and using different metrics or evaluation approaches could yield varied interpretations of efficiency and carbon emissions.

5 AI ENGINEERING WITH CEMAI

In this section, we analyzed and discussed how CEMAI addresses the new AI engineering dimensions in Section 2.2.

Energy Consumption: CodeCarbon, integrated into CEMAI, tracks energy usage in the pipeline using techniques like function decorators for continuous monitoring and explicit objects requiring start and end calls. It monitors energy on GPUs using the Python library `pynvml` [8], estimates RAM energy consumption using a rule of thumb (approximately three watts per 8GB of DDR3 or DDR4 memory [6]), and monitors CPUs using Intel Performance Counter [39] (instead of Intel Power Gadget) or Intel RAPL files [26] on Linux). In the absence of specific tools, it estimates CPU energy consumption using a database of 2000+ Intel and AMD CPUs and their thermal design power values (TDP). If a CPU is not found in the database, CodeCarbon assumes that 50% of the TDP will be the average power consumption for approximation. The net energy used is measured as the net power supply consumed during the compute time, expressed in kWh. Although CEMAI does not explicitly monitor energy consumption, it relies on carbon emissions measurement as a derived quantity.

Carbon Emission Measurement: CEMAI uses CodeCarbon for estimating carbon emissions during code execution, considering two main factors: *Carbon Intensity (C)* and *Energy Consumed (E)*. Carbon intensity represents the CO₂ emitted per kilowatt-hour of electricity consumed, calculated as a weighted average of emissions from various energy sources. The carbon intensity values for different sources include Coal (995 kg/MWh), Petroleum (816 kg/MWh), Natural Gas (743 kg/MWh), Geothermal (38 kg/MWh), Hydroelectricity (26 kg/MWh), Nuclear (29 kg/MWh), Solar (48 kg/MWh), and Wind (26 kg/MWh). The Net Carbon Intensity is computed based on the energy mix of the grid electricity. Energy consumed quantifies the energy used by the computational infrastructure in kilowatt-hours. Carbon dioxide emissions (gCO₂eq) are derived by multiplying C and E (see Tables 2- 4 for gCO₂eq in our datasets).

Algorithm Efficiency: Our pipeline configuration, with carbon emissions and ML performance measurement, identifies algorithms

with optimal performance in relation to carbon emissions. Experimental findings indicate that feature-engineered models generally perform better but emit more CO₂. DT models emerge as the most carbon-efficient, contrasting with LSTM models that exhibit higher emissions and lower performance. This underscores a trade-off between environmental impact and algorithmic effectiveness.

Data Impact: We observe distinct carbon emission patterns for the data processing stages of CEMAI in our datasets. The Profile and Clean stages consistently exhibit low emissions. The Featureize stage shows considerable variation, such as emissions ranging from 0.00000 to 0.00132 gCO₂eq in the Bosch CNC dataset, indicating the impact of feature engineering complexity. Other stages like Split, Scale, Sequentialize, and Combine generally have lower emissions but vary based on the dataset and model. For example, the Scale stage in the Broaching dataset ranges from 0.00001 to 0.00363 gCO₂eq. These variations highlight the influence of dataset size, complexity, and processing requirements on carbon emissions, emphasizing the need to consider environmental impacts in ML data processing workflows.

Infrastructure Location: CEMAI’s emissions are influenced by the geographical location, impacting the carbon intensity of electricity. We conducted our experiments in a country known for its clean energy profile (primarily sourced from renewables), which led to low carbon intensity. Tables 2- 4 show estimated emissions. If the infrastructure had been in a region with higher carbon intensity (e.g., coal-dependent countries), emissions would have been higher. Crucially, model performance remains unaffected by location or associated emissions, focusing solely on accuracy.

Scalability: We adopted a linear scaling approach in CEMAI using CodeCarbon to estimate carbon emissions for varying dataset sizes. This approach involves initially determining baseline emissions for each model and dataset, as provided in Tables 2- 4. These baseline figures are multiplied by scaling factors (1 million, 1 billion, 1 trillion) to project emissions for increased dataset sizes. For example, with the DT model on the Bosch CNC dataset, the baseline emission of 0.01409 gCO₂eq is scaled linearly to approximately 14,090.39 gCO₂eq for a dataset 1 million times larger, 14,090,393.36 gCO₂eq for 1 billion times, and 14,090,393,364.42 gCO₂eq for 1 trillion times larger dataset. While this method provides a basic framework for scaling emissions estimates, it assumes linear growth, which may not always hold due to algorithm optimization, hardware efficiency, and other operational efficiencies. Therefore, actual figures may vary in real time.

Model Deployment: When a model is deployed as a Docker container with CEMAI, only the data pre-processing stages and model inference occur. Analyzing carbon emissions for CEMAI across our datasets, emissions due to deployment range from 0.196 gCO₂eq for XGBoost to 12.464 gCO₂eq for LSTM with feature engineering. These figures cover the entire ML pipeline, emphasizing notably higher emissions for LSTM models.

Optimization Strategies: CEMAI utilizes DVC for *green pipeline orchestration*, featuring intermediate output caching, avoidance of redundant stages, and *smart caching* for configuration-based optimization. This streamlines pipeline management, enhancing efficiency and curtailing carbon emissions by avoiding unnecessary recomputation. Additionally, understanding carbon emissions at different ML pipeline stages is crucial for optimization, facilitating

the choice of models that balance performance and carbon efficiency. It can guide the optimization of feature engineering and hyperparameters, reducing computational demands and emissions.

Having CodeCarbon for precise carbon emissions tracking throughout the ML lifecycle, CEMAI ensures a holistic evaluation, including data preprocessing, model training, and inference stages. DVC’s orchestration capabilities contribute to the optimization of energy consumption by efficiently managing pipeline stages and avoiding unnecessary reruns. Implementing Green AI metrics provides users with comprehensive insights, allowing informed decisions that balance predictive accuracy with environmental impact.

6 RELATED WORK

This paper focuses on the intersection of AI’s carbon footprint and the need for sustainable engineering practices amid heightened concerns about the environmental impact of AI. Existing frameworks, like the carbon footprint estimation framework by Lannelongue et al. [15], while valuable, often lack comprehensive coverage of the ML development lifecycle, limiting practical applicability by focusing solely on computational aspects. Similarly, the work by Tornede et al. [41] addresses sustainable AutoML theoretically, lacking empirical evidence for the effectiveness of proposed strategies.

Naidu et al. [22] investigated additional energy costs associated with incorporating differential privacy in privacy-preserving ML, yet their focus is limited and does not consider other energy-intensive aspects like model architecture or hardware variations. Anselmo et al. [1] proposed a data-centric method to minimize carbon output during deep learning data preparation. However, its scalability and applicability across diverse data modalities or tasks are not explored, leaving a gap in practical generalization. Wu et al. [43] addressed the broader environmental implications of AI’s growth but lacked benchmarked solutions or quantitative analysis for various applications. In medical imaging, Selvan et al. [34] quantified carbon emissions involved in training deep learning models, highlighting the potential of Bayesian optimization for carbon footprint reduction. However, their research does not cover the entire spectrum of medical image analysis operations, such as data annotation or model inference. Lastly, Polyzotis et al. [25] highlighted data lifecycle challenges in production ML without exploring their connection to energy consumption or carbon emissions.

To bridge the gaps mentioned above, we introduce CEMAI, an ML pipeline that comprehensively minimizes carbon emissions throughout the entire ML process. Unlike traditional approaches that primarily focus on training, CEMAI extends this scope to encompass inference, data preprocessing, and post-processing stages. By leveraging CodeCarbon [5] with enhanced granularity, it offers a more nuanced understanding of real-world ML applications. CEMAI’s integration with DVC allows for real-time carbon emission evaluations, offering insights into energy optimization across diverse hardware setups. Through empirical IIoT studies, examining anomaly detection and predictive maintenance tasks, we highlight carbon-intensive pipeline stages and illuminate trade-offs between computational efficiency, model accuracy, and environmental impact. Our work not only identifies gaps in addressing carbon footprints but also provides practical, empirically validated solutions, paving the way for carbon emission-aware AI engineering.

7 IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Continual Learning. A potential future direction for CEMAI involves integrating continual learning into the ML pipeline. Continual learning aims to enable AI systems to continuously learn from new data without forgetting past knowledge [11, 38]. By adapting to changing data and conditions, CEMAI can update models rather than training new models, and thereby minimize unnecessary energy consumption. The pipeline could be designed to identify shifts in data, update models, and adjust configurations based on environmental impact, fostering adaptability while maintaining an eco-conscious approach to ML model enhancements.

Transfer Learning. Another potential future avenue for CEMAI involves leveraging transfer learning strategies to reduce the environmental impact of ML model development. Applying transfer learning within CEMAI could focus on reusing and repurposing pre-trained models or knowledge from related domains to minimize the need for extensive retraining and computational resources. Specifically, transfer learning could involve techniques to extract and utilize knowledge from pre-existing models trained on similar or related tasks or datasets. The goal would be to transfer this knowledge to new tasks or domains within CEMAI, reducing the demand for extensive training from scratch.

Multi-objective Optimization. The future work on multi-objective optimization for CEMAI aims to optimize ML models by considering both performance and sustainability factors. It involves finding solutions that balance high performance with reduced energy consumption and carbon emissions. The process includes developing algorithms to identify trade-offs between objectives and seek model configurations that balance performance with lower environmental impact. It requires advanced algorithms to navigate these trade-offs and may involve methodologies to generate diverse solutions, allowing users to choose models aligning with specific performance and environmental preferences.

8 CONCLUSION

In the pursuit of environmentally responsible AI engineering, this paper has introduced a novel approach that harmonizes performance optimization with the reduction of carbon emissions in ML pipelines. Through the development and application of CEMAI, we underscored the critical importance of assessing and mitigating the environmental impact of ML systems. Our research demonstrates the efficacy of using carbon emissions as a guiding metric for configuring ML pipelines that excel in performance while maintaining low emissions. However, we acknowledge that several challenges persist in accurately quantifying emissions across the entire ML pipeline, including inference phases, real-time decision-making, and hardware variations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work has been conducted as part of the ENFIELD project (101120657) funded by the European Commission within the H2020 Programme.

REFERENCES

- [1] Martin Anselmo and Monica Vitali. 2023. A Data-Centric Approach for Reducing Carbon Emissions in Deep Learning. In *International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering*. Springer, 123–138.

- [2] Lasse F Wolff Anthony, Benjamin Kanding, and Raghavendra Selvan. 2020. Carbontracker: Tracking and predicting the carbon footprint of training deep learning models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.03051* (2020).
- [3] Jan Bosch, Helena Holmström Olsson, and Ivica Crnkovic. 2021. Engineering AI systems: A research agenda. In *Artificial Intelligence Paradigms for Smart Cyber-Physical Systems*. 1–19.
- [4] Anita D Carleton, Erin Harper, Tim Menzies, Tao Xie, Sigrid Eldh, and Michael R Lyu. 2020. The AI Effect: Working at the Intersection of AI and SE. *IEEE Software* 37, 4 (2020), 26–35.
- [5] Code Carbon. Visited in 2023. <https://codecarbon.io/>.
- [6] Crucial. Visited in 2023. <https://www.crucial.com/support/articles-faq-memory/how-much-power-does-memory-use>.
- [7] Rudresh Dwivedi, Devam Dave, Het Naik, Smriti Singhal, Omer Rana, Pankesh Patel, Bin Qian, Zhenyu Wen, Tejal Shah, Graham Morgan, et al. 2022. Explainable AI (XAI): core ideas, techniques and solutions. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* (2022).
- [8] Lucia Bouza Huguete, Aurélie Bugeau, and Loïc Lannelongue. 2023. How to estimate carbon footprint when training deep learning models? A guide and review. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.08323* (2023).
- [9] Sepp Hochreiter and Jürgen Schmidhuber. 1997. Long short-term memory. *Neural computation* 9, 8 (1997), 1735–1780.
- [10] Angela Horneman, Andrew Mellinger, and Ipek Ozkaya. 2020. *AI Engineering: 11 Foundational Practices*. Technical Report. Carnegie Mellon University Pittsburgh United States.
- [11] Erik Johannes Husom, Sagar Sen, Arda Goknil, Simeon Tverdal, and Phu Nguyen. 2023. REPTILE: a Tool for Replay-driven Continual Learning in IIoT. In *IoT'23*.
- [12] Mauro Isaja, Phu Nguyen, Arda Goknil, Sagar Sen, Erik Johannes Husom, Simeon Tverdal, Abhilash Anand, Yunman Jiang, Karl John Pedersen, Per Myrseth, et al. 2023. A blockchain-based framework for trusted quality data sharing towards zero-defect manufacturing. *Computers in Industry* 146 (2023), 103853.
- [13] iterative.ai. Visited in 2022. Open-source Version Control System for Machine Learning Projects. <https://dvc.org/>.
- [14] Ruslan Kupriev, Dmitry Petrov, Pawel Redzyński, Saugat Pachhai, Casper da Costa-Luis, Alexander Schepanovski, Peter Rowlands, Ivan Shcheklein, Jorge Orpinel, Fábio Santos, Aman Sharma, Zhanibek, Gao, Batuhan Taskaya, Dani Hodovic, Andrew Grigorev, Earl, Nabanita Dash, nik123, George Vyshnya, maykulkarni, Max Hora, Vera, Sanidhya Mangal, Wojciech Baranowski, Clemens Wolff, Alex Maslakov, Alex Khamutov, Kurian Benoy, and Ophir Yoktan. 2021. DVC: Data Version Control - Git for Data & Models. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4544110>.
- [15] Loïc Lannelongue and Michael Inouye. 2023. Carbon footprint estimation for computational research. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers* 3, 1 (2023), 9.
- [16] Yann LeCun et al. 1989. Generalization and network design strategies. *Connectionism in perspective* 19 (1989), 143–155.
- [17] Yann A LeCun, Léon Bottou, Genevieve B Orr, and Klaus-Robert Müller. 2012. Efficient backprop. In *Neural networks: Tricks of the trade*. 9–48.
- [18] Carl H Lubba, Sarab S Sethi, Philip Knaute, Simon R Schultz, Ben D Fulcher, and Nick S Jones. 2019. catch22: Canonical time-series characteristics. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 33, 6 (2019), 1821–1852.
- [19] Scott M Lundberg, Gabriel G Erion, and Su-In Lee. 2018. Consistent individualized feature attribution for tree ensembles. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03888* (2018).
- [20] Scott M Lundberg and Su-In Lee. 2017. A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 30, I. Guyon, U. V. Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. Vishwanathan, and R. Garnett (Eds.). Curran Associates, Inc., 4765–4774. <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/7062-a-unified-approach-to-interpreting-model-predictions.pdf>
- [21] Scott M Lundberg and Su-In Lee. 2017. A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 30 (2017).
- [22] Rakshit Naidu, Harshita Diddee, Ajinkya Mulay, Aleti Vardhan, Krithika Ramesh, and Ahmed Zamzam. 2021. Towards quantifying the carbon emissions of differentially private machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2107.06946* (2021).
- [23] Bo Pang, Erik Nijkamp, and Ying Nian Wu. 2020. Deep learning with tensorflow: A review. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics* 45, 2 (2020), 227–248.
- [24] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and E. Duchesnay. 2011. Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 12 (2011), 2825–2830.
- [25] Neoklis Polyzotis, Sudip Roy, Steven Euijong Whang, and Martin Zinkevich. 2018. Data lifecycle challenges in production machine learning: a survey. *ACM SIGMOD Record* 47, 2 (2018), 17–28.
- [26] RAPL. Visited in 2023. <https://web.eece.maine.edu/~vwweaver/projects/rapl/>.
- [27] David N Reshef, Yakir A Reshef, Hilary K Finucane, Sharon R Grossman, Gilean McVean, Peter J Turnbaugh, Eric S Lander, Michael Mitzenmacher, and Pardis C Sabeti. 2011. Detecting novel associations in large data sets. *science* 334, 6062 (2011), 1518–1524.
- [28] Marco Tulio Ribeiro, Sameer Singh, and Carlos Guestrin. 2016. "Why should I trust you?" Explaining the predictions of any classifier. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining*. 1135–1144.
- [29] Marco Tulio Ribeiro, Sameer Singh, and Carlos Guestrin. 2018. Anchors: High-precision model-agnostic explanations. In *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*, Vol. 32.
- [30] Hannah Ritchie and Pablo Rosado. 2020. Electricity Mix. *Our World in Data* (2020). <https://ourworldindata.org/electricity-mix>.
- [31] Alvin E Roth. 1988. *The Shapley value: essays in honor of Lloyd S. Shapley*. Cambridge University Press.
- [32] Roy Schwartz, Jesse Dodge, Noah A Smith, and Oren Etzioni. 2020. Green ai. *Commun. ACM* 63, 12 (2020), 54–63.
- [33] Philip Sedgwick. 2012. Pearson's correlation coefficient. *Bmj* 345 (2012).
- [34] Raghavendra Selvan, Nikhil Bhagwat, Lasse F Wolff Anthony, Benjamin Kanding, and Erik B Dam. 2022. Carbon footprint of selecting and training deep learning models for medical image analysis. In *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*. Springer, 506–516.
- [35] Sagar Sen, Erik Johannes Husom, Arda Goknil, Dimitra Politaki, Simeon Tverdal, Phu Nguyen, and Nicolas Jourdan. 2023. Virtual sensors for erroneous data repair in manufacturing a machine learning pipeline. *Computers in Industry* 149 (2023), 103917.
- [36] Sagar Sen, Erik Johannes Husom, Arda Goknil, Simeon Tverdal, and Phu Nguyen. 2023. Uncertainty-aware Virtual Sensors for Cyber-Physical Systems. *IEEE Software* (2023).
- [37] Sagar Sen, Erik Johannes Husom, Arda Goknil, Simeon Tverdal, Phu Nguyen, and Iker Mancisidor. 2022. Taming Data Quality in AI-Enabled Industrial Internet of Things. *IEEE Software* 39, 6 (2022), 35–42.
- [38] Sagar Sen, Simon Myklebust Nielsen, Erik Johannes Husom, Arda Goknil, Simeon Tverdal, and Leonardo Sastoque Pinilla. 2023. Replay-driven continual learning for the industrial internet of things. In *2023 IEEE/ACM 2nd International Conference on AI Engineering-Software Engineering for AI (CAIN)*. IEEE, 43–55.
- [39] Arsalan Shahid, Muhammad Fahad, Ravi Reddy Manumachu, and Alexey Lastovetsky. 2020. A comparative study of techniques for energy predictive modeling using performance monitoring counters on modern multicore CPUs. *IEEE Access* 8 (2020), 143306–143332.
- [40] Mohamed-Ali Tnani, Michael Feil, and Klaus Diepold. 2022. Smart Data Collection System for Brownfield CNC Milling Machines: A New Benchmark Dataset for Data-Driven Machine Monitoring. *Procedia CIRP* 107 (2022), 131–136.
- [41] Tanja Tornede, Alexander Tornede, Jonas Hanselle, Felix Mohr, Marcel Wever, and Eyke Hüllermeier. 2023. Towards green automated machine learning: Status quo and future directions. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research* 77 (2023), 427–457.
- [42] Simeon Tverdal, Arda Goknil, Phu Nguyen, Erik Johannes Husom, Jan Ruh, and Francesca Flamigni. 2023. Edge-based Data Profiling and Repair as a Service for IoT. In *IoT'23*.
- [43] Carole-Jean Wu, Romya Raghavendra, Udit Gupta, Bilge Acun, Newsha Ardalani, Kiwan Maeng, Gloria Chang, Fiona Aga, Jinshi Huang, Charles Bai, et al. 2022. Sustainable ai: Environmental implications, challenges and opportunities. *Proceedings of Machine Learning and Systems* 4 (2022), 795–813.
- [44] Jingjing Xu, Wangchunshu Zhou, Zhiyi Fu, Hao Zhou, and Lei Li. 2021. A survey on green deep learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.05193* (2021).